

THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO THE STUDY OF TOLERANCE IN CONTEMPORARY RELIGIOUS-PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH

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Abstract

This article discusses the theoretical and methodological analysis of the concept of religious tolerance. Also, various psychological and religious approaches to the phenomenon of religious tolerance have been comparatively analyzed.

Key words: religion, tolerance, religious tolerance, psychological character, trust, approach

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается теоретико-методологический анализ понятия религиозной толерантности. Также сравнительно проанализированы различные психологические и религиозные подходы к феномену религиозной толерантности.

Ключевые слова: религия, толерантность, религиозная толерантность, психологический характер, доверие, подход.

It is known that the concept of tolerance is the subject of interdisciplinary research, and its research creates a unique integration of information on the problem. Until now, there are many definitions of the phenomenon of tolerance, and most of the researches were carried out in philosophical, sociological and pedagogical contexts, in which the system of human values was more taken into account. However, the concept of "tolerance" is considered a purely psychological concept, and studying the foundations of its formation is likely to shed light on

many controversial views on the concept.

Therefore, it is necessary to clarify the peculiarities of the concepts of tolerance and religious tolerance. These concepts must be carefully distinguished, because manipulators (including most politicians) call for tolerance from lies, because it is easier to control people who are loyal to everything. In addition, according to the Declaration of "Principles of Tolerance" adopted at the General Conference of UNESCO in 1995, "tolerance" means correct understanding and acceptance, respect for the diversity of world cultures, forms of self-expression, and ways of expressing human individuality..., which harmony and diversity, this is the kindness that makes it possible to achieve peace and is sympathetic to the exchange of the culture of war with the culture of peace"[3].

There are different approaches in describing the concept of tolerance. In particular, in Russian, tolerance (given as an "outdated concept" in some dictionaries) is interpreted as patience for points of view that do not correspond to the subject's position, such as patience as a concept opposite to impatience. In national cultural contexts, the meanings of mercy and forgiveness are attached to the characteristic features of patience. Latin etymological dictionaries and dictionaries of European languages show the meaning of toleration in 2 different terms, that is, "patience" and "support"[3].

The world is wide, there are many countries in the world, but our unique motherland, Uzbekistan, is the only one in this world. The uniqueness of the country called Uzbekistan is reflected in its unique nature, rich history, hardworking people, and the fact that representatives of different nationalities and peoples live on this land as children of a single family. Such harmony, friendship and cooperation have their deep historical roots and foundation. These principles are enshrined in the Constitution of our country. In particular, its 18th article states that all citizens have the same rights and freedoms and are equal before the law regardless of gender, race, nationality, religion, social origin, belief, personality

and social status. The concept of tolerance has been defined by experts in various fields[1]. For example, tolerance in a philosophical sense is derived from the Latin word "tolerantia" which means endurance, endurance, toleration, tolerance, and expresses the concepts of tolerance, meekness and benevolence in philosophy.

The word "tolerance" entered the Russian language relatively recently. F.A. Brockhaus and I.A. In Efron's encyclopedic dictionary published in 1909, "tolerance" supposedly means tolerance of a particular religious worldview. V. Dahl's dictionary defines "forbearance" as a quality or quality, the ability to bear with something or someone "only out of pity or complacency." S.I. In Ojegov's dictionary, the word tolerance is an analogue of the word tolerance, which expresses the ability of a person to be in a peaceful relationship without enmity to someone's opinion and character. Based on the above, it can be noted that the words "tolerance" and "endurance" are synonyms[2].

Analyzing the boundaries of these concepts, i.e., the size of its content, determining the part that reflects reality, is another problem of defining the concept. The problem of tolerance limits has been considered by many researchers who have studied it. For example, Plato described the "paradox of endurance": unlimited endurance must lead to loss of endurance. If one is not infinitely resistant to the resistant and is willing to protect the resistant team from the resistant, then the resistant will be ruined. K. on this problem. Popper said: "on the path of tolerance, it is necessary to declare the right not to be resistant to the unbearable." V.A. Tishkov says that tolerance is not about allowing everything and forgiving all sins, but tolerance includes active action against extreme forms of intolerance. Researchers G.U. Soldatova connects the problem of limits of tolerance with the problem of limits of tolerance and indifference, conformism, indifference. Resilience and indifference are mutually exclusive concepts, that is, tolerance implies the recognition of another opposing position, another point of view. In this case, the individual does not agree with another, second opinion, but recognizes its

right to exist.

A positive understanding of tolerance is achieved by identifying its opposite - intolerance or intolerance, based on a firm belief that one's own system of views, lifestyle, group to which one belongs is superior to all others. In modern psychological and philosophical literature, the question of endurance limits has been a controversial issue for the following reasons:

1. The concept of tolerance is polymodal, there is no universally accepted definition.

2. According to ethical origin, "tolerance" is an evaluative category. We judge ourselves, other people, and our own and others' actions in accordance with our accepted positions. For example, love, compassion, empathy, etc. are positive values recognized by all. Betrayal, hatred, malice and the like are undesirable behaviors. But these values are also abstract enough that it is difficult to determine the limit of tolerance for them.

3. When values are not universally recognized, it becomes more difficult to determine the limits of endurance. It is difficult to evaluate social events and actions such as euthanasia, lying for salvation, abortion, saving the lives of patients with irreversible severe pathologies, conducting experiments on animals from the point of view of "good and bad".

4. It is not really possible to determine the limits of tolerance when discussing the values that are important for a person.

The problem of tolerance is complex, and there is no single solution beyond which tolerance loses its significance and strictly establishes the limit of all possible actions.

Yu.A. Ishchenko sees endurance as "practical norm of communication". He argues that resilience is a universal human value that increases in importance in terms of a person's self-awareness and becomes more relevant during times of dramatic life change. V.O. According to Tishkov, tolerance is related to the self-

awareness of a person, his unity in activity and communication. V.O. Tishkov tries to define the subject of tolerance in his work "On Tolerance". For the subject, tolerance is "not an inherent group or individual characteristic, but a constant and directed effort to construct and implement certain personal and general values and moral norms"[5].

Solving the problems of national intolerance, I.B. Gasanov calls tolerance the antipode of aggressiveness, and representatives of neo-Freudianism: V. Reich, K. Horney, G. Marcuse, A. Mitterlich, N. Brown, A. Bullock, E. Fromm. Based on the works of Fromm, he substantiates the social connection of these personal qualities, and concludes that aggression is the basis of enmity, and tolerance is the basis of pacifism.

V.M. Zolotukhin in his work "Two Concepts of Tolerance", analyzes the essence of the concept of "tolerance", calculates and recognizes the multidimensionality of social life, and determines the philosophical content of tolerance. According to him, tolerance is, on the one hand, a moral principle that governs human activity and forms a special type of worldview, and on the other hand, it is a practical instrument that allows effective resolution of conflicts[5].

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